

Abstract

Climate change and increasing energy demands necessitate sustainable energy solutions. Egypt, with its favorable climatic conditions, holds significant potential for solar energy production. This paper investigates strategies to optimize solar farm performance in Egypt, focusing on environmental factors such as aerosols/dust storms and clouds. Utilizing satellite data, the study aims to enhance the efficiency of PV installation with Benban Solar Park as a use-case.

Introduction

- Background: Climate change and energy demand are global and national challenges. Egypt's climatic advantage for solar energy production and reduce fossil fuel dependency.
- Purpose: Identify and mitigate environmental factors affecting solar energy yields. Utilize satellite and remote sensing data to enhance solar farm performance.
- Hypotheses: Aerosols, dust storms and overcast significantly impact PV energy production. Strategic monitoring and maintenance can mitigate these impacts.

Challenges in Solar Energy Production

	High temperatures negatively affect PV systems.	<p>➤ Optimization Strategies: PV Orientation & Maintenance</p> <p>➤ Advanced Monitoring Systems: Integration of weather forecasting data for real-time management.</p>
	Structural integrity against high wind speeds.	
	Effective drainage systems to for rainwater damage	
	Aerosol, Dust & Cloud Events: Impact on GHI Seasonal Variations: Directly Effect Energy Yields	

Method

	Satellite & Remote Sensing for Benban Area: MODIS, CAMS from Jan. 2014 to Jan. 2024 Daily Data. PVGIS Yearly Data.
	Data Preprocessing: MODIS, CAMS → Monthly Periods (10y. AVG). PVGIS → Extrapolation for 3.8TWh Annual Capacity.
	Computations, Results and Analysis: Aerosol & Cloud Modification Factors. Monthly & Yearly Visualizations for Energy Losses

Results

Monthly Variations and Energy Losses:

- Aerosol Modification Factor (AMF)
- Cloud Modification Factor (CMF)
- Lowest AMF values: between May and June → Minimal aerosol impact.
- Peaked CMF values: December, January, and March → significant energy losses due to cloud cover.

- Aggregated studied metrics annually:
- Contrasting potential energy production with actual estimated production due to environmental impacts.
 - Environmental impacts: estimated actual output at 2.95 TWh, with aerosols contributing 718.9 GWh while clouds contributing 128.8 GWh in losses.

- Juxtaposed optimal energy production against estimated energy losses for each month, where losses are broken down to totals & subtotals:
- Seasonal variability in maximum energy production potential & corresponding losses.
 - Peak energy production: February (332.1 GWh), June (341.08 GWh), and July (348.67 GWh)
 - Respective losses: 73.07 GWh, 81.27 GWh, and 76.32 GWh, primarily due to aerosols.

Discussion

➤ Summary:

- Egypt's potential for solar energy production is substantial but challenged by environmental factors.
- Aerosols and dust have a more significant impact than clouds on solar energy yields.

➤ Seasonal Energy Reductions:

- The most substantial reductions in energy production were observed in February, May, and June, with respective losses of 24.9%, 24.6%, and 23.8%.
- Aerosols had a more pronounced impact on energy production, particularly affecting the solar output during high dust activity seasons such as spring and early summer.

➤ Implications:

- Real-time monitoring and strategic maintenance can mitigate energy losses.
- Importance of considering environmental variability in solar farm design.

Conclusion

➤ Key Findings:

- Aerosols and dust storms are major factors affecting solar energy production in Egypt.
- Strategic planning and real-time monitoring are crucial for optimizing solar farm efficiency.

➤ Future Directions:

- Further research on the impact of environmental factors on solar energy.
- Development of more resilient and efficient solar farm designs.
- Embedding remote and satellite sensing for live data and forecasting (existing ML models) for strategic planning.

References

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Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the EU-funded CIROCCO project under Grant Agreement No. 101086497.